

Lebanese Chemistry Teachers' Perceptions of Experiments, Practices and Challenges in Implementing Lab Work

Rim Hammoud (Lebanese University)

E-mail: reem.hammoud@ul.edu.lb

ORCID record: <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-0507-5888>

Abstract:

This research investigated Lebanese chemistry teachers' perceptions of chemistry experiments, explored their practices in conducting lab work, and examined the challenges they face in integrating these activities into their teaching. This study adopted a descriptive analytical approach, and a questionnaire was used for data collection and analysis. A total of 118 chemistry teachers completed the questionnaire. Our findings revealed that teachers predominantly view experiments through a traditional scientific method lens, emphasizing hypothesis validation and problem-solving over exploration and discovery. Additionally, the study highlighted that teachers occasionally conduct lab work, viewing it as a supplementary activity rather than an essential component of their teaching practices. Their teaching practices in conducting lab work emerge as a predominantly teacher-centered approach where lab work is implemented as a confirmatory activity through a "recipe" style to verify previously taught concepts. The findings also underscore logistical and resource-related challenges that teachers frequently face in integrating lab work into their teaching. These results underscore the need for ongoing support and training for teachers to effectively implement lab work into their practices.

Keywords: Chemistry education, Perceptions, Experiments, Lab work, Challenges.

Introduction

Chemistry experiments are considered a fundamental component of chemistry teaching, offering students opportunities to link theoretical knowledge with practical applications that make chemical concepts concrete. Studies have shown that conducting chemistry experiments enables students to understand their environment, engage in hands-on activities, develop problem-solving skills, and improve both psychomotor and cognitive abilities (McDonnell et al., 2007; Moutsakis et al., 2024). This approach also promotes meaningful learning and strengthens the connection between chemistry and everyday life, thus promoting lasting learning and the development of students' science process skills (Harman et al., 2016), particularly if experiments are carried out as part of an inquiry-type laboratory (Hofstein et al., 2004).

Laboratories are one of the basic environments for conducting experiments. Laboratory work (lab work) and other forms of practical work in science education have been widely studied over the last decades in many countries (Duban et al., 2019; Lunetta et al., 2007; Marzin-Janvier & Kermen, 2015). The terms "laboratory work" and "practical work" are frequently used in the literature without precise definitions, covering a wide range of activities (Hofstein & Mamlok-Naaman,

Received: 03 February 2025

Revised: 12 February 2025

Accepted: 18 February 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14885660>

2007). In this study, these terms are used as synonyms to designate any type of laboratory activity that teachers can implement in a chemistry classroom.

As Shah (2007) stated, it would be rare to find any science course in any institution of education without a substantial component of lab work. Since chemistry is an experimental science, laboratory activities have long been regarded as essential for learning chemistry (Crawford & Kloepper, 2019; Johnstone & Al-Shuaili, 2001; Nakhleh et al., 2002; Sneddon & Hill, 2011). Beside the lectures, it is very important that the chemistry teacher implements lab work because, as many researchers have pointed out, better results for the students can be achieved thanks to laboratory activities (Hofstein & Lunetta, 2004; Lazarowitz & Tamir, 1994).

In secondary education, laboratory activities play a crucial role in enhancing the learning experience. They help students develop practical skills, improve conceptual understanding, promote scientific inquiry abilities, and increase interest in chemistry (Abrahams & Millar, 2008; Gericke et al., 2022), which leads to better chemistry comprehension and greater student engagement with the subject (Hofstein & Hugerat, 2021). However, despite its educational importance, the implementation of lab work often encounters challenges, particularly in resource-limited settings such as Lebanon.

In the Lebanese context, chemistry is delivered separately from other sciences (physics and biology) starting from grade seven and is taught either in English or French (depending on whether the school is French or English-speaking). The Lebanese curriculum highlights the importance of practical skills in chemistry education and advocates the use of student-centered approaches to teaching (Ayoubi & BouJaoude, 2006), with an emphasis given to hands-on and minds-on science (BouJaoude, 2002). Nonetheless, the successful implementation of lab work in the classroom largely depends on teachers' perceptions of its value and feasibility (Prabha, 2016), and the challenges they encounter (Saad & BouJaoude, 2012). This study investigated Lebanese chemistry teachers' perceptions of chemistry experiments, explored their practices in conducting lab work, and examined the challenges they face in integrating these activities into their teaching.

Literature review

Chemistry teachers' perceptions toward experiments

Experiments are a fundamental component of scientific practice, involving systematic observation and manipulation of variables to gather data and draw conclusions (Wei & Li, 2017). They are designed to support, refute, or validate hypotheses (Mayo, 1996). From the perspective of the epistemology of science, an experiment is typically considered as a planned intervention designed to test a prediction based on a theory or hypothesis (Abrahams & Millar, 2008). In their study, Wei & Li (2017) identify multiple dimensions that characterize experiments, including conceptual, epistemological, procedural, safety, temporal, and pedagogical aspects. These dimensions reflect the various factors that influence how experiments are perceived and conducted in educational settings.

Teachers' perceptions play a crucial role in how they approach and prioritize laboratory work within their classrooms. Research shows that teachers who consider experiments to be an essential part of the learning process are more likely to design and carry out meaningful laboratory activities (Abrahams & Millar, 2008). These perceptions are influenced by their own educational experiences, opportunities for professional development, and their understanding of the purpose

of experimentation in chemistry education. Although previous studies have examined teachers' perceptions of laboratory work in general (e.g. Duban et al., 2019), there is limited research specifically focused on how teachers define and attribute characteristics to chemistry experiments. This distinction is important because it sheds light on the pedagogical values and priorities that guide teachers' educational decisions.

Teachers' practices in conducting lab work

There is no single method for classifying chemistry experiments. Many chemists agree that experiments can be classified into three groups: teacher demonstrations, cookbook/recipe experiments, and open-ended/inquiry experiments (Köller et al., 2015). Similar classifications of laboratory activities found in the literature include a variety of types such as demonstrations, teacher-directed experiments, and investigations that are directed by either the teacher or the students (Gott & Duggan, 2007). These classifications emphasize that the level of teacher guidance and instruction can vary from highly structured and teacher-centered approaches to more open-ended inquiry methods.

Domin (1999) analyzes laboratory instruction styles in science education, categorizing them into four teaching approaches: expository, inquiry-based, discovery, and problem-based. The expository style, a traditional and highly structured approach, involves teacher-directed activities where students follow predetermined instructions to achieve specific outcomes. It has been known by other terms such as verification, cookbook or recipe style and it is the most usual way to implement lab work (Köller et al., 2015; Tobin, 1990), but has been criticized for promoting lower-order cognitive skills (Hofstein et al., 2004). In contrast, the inquiry-based style, a student-centered approach, encourages learners to investigate scientific questions and create the procedure with minimal guidance, fostering critical thinking. The discovery style guides students to a predetermined conclusion through structured activities, while inquiry allows for open-ended exploration. The problem-based style combines lab work with real-world issues, requiring collaboration among students to develop a deep understanding of concepts. It follows a deductive approach, meaning that students are expected to have prior knowledge of the concepts involved before tackling the problem. Domin (1999) concludes that no single laboratory instruction style is inherently superior to the others. The effectiveness of each style depends on its appropriate use in the right context (Domin, 2007) considering the instructional goals, the level of student expertise, and the desired balance between concept mastery and skill development.

Many science educators have advocated for more open-ended experiments to help students develop their scientific skills (Abd-El-Khalick et al., 2004; Hofstein et al., 2004). However, most laboratory work in schools continues to follow a traditional "recipe" style (Köller et al., 2015; Wei & Li, 2017), where practical work is often used primarily for verifying or confirming existing theories or for discovering objectively knowable facts (Prabha, 2016; Yeşiloğlu & Köseoğlu, 2020). In their study that evaluated the undergraduate chemistry laboratory manuals in a private university in Lebanon, Arnous & Ayoubi (2018) highlighted that almost all the experiments focused on the lowest levels of inquiry and are typically verification "exercises" where students are just following instructions and procedural directions. Based on similar findings, Abrahams & Millar (2008) concluded that teachers' emphasis on lab work consisted mainly of making students manipulate physical objects and equipment, but rarely addressed the cognitive challenge of linking

observations and experiments to conceptual ideas or developing students' understanding of scientific inquiry procedures.

Teaching practices in laboratory work have evolved significantly, particularly in response to challenges such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Various methodologies in which technology is used, including simulated, virtual and remote laboratories, have been implemented as alternatives or supplements for traditional face-to-face laboratories to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes (Wei et al., 2019). However, this study focused on the perceptions and practices of chemistry teachers in the context of a traditional face-to-face laboratory setting.

Challenges of implementing lab work in chemistry education

Despite advancements in science education and improvements in teachers' professional knowledge and classroom practices, challenges related to the effective and appropriate use of laboratory work remain insufficiently addressed (Hofstein et al., 2013). These challenges, which range from logistical issues to pedagogical concerns, affect both students and educators.

Many schools face shortages of fundamental laboratory equipment and chemicals (Hassan et al., 2017; Nsanzimana et al., 2021). This lack of resources limits teachers' ability to involve students in useful hands-on activities, often forcing them to focus on theoretical instruction over practical work (Nkurunziza et al., 2023; Shana & Abulibdeh, 2020). Insufficient laboratory facilities, including overcrowded labs and lack of proper maintenance, hinder the successful implementation of lab work (Ajayi, 2008; Pareek, 2019). Additionally, other issues like inadequate storage for chemicals and equipment exacerbate the situation (Alema et al., 2024), while budget limitations restrict schools from acquiring essential materials and improving laboratory infrastructure (Nsanzimana et al., 2021).

Besides, a lack of qualified laboratory technicians limits the support for teachers during lab sessions (Chala, 2019), and affects the overall safety and effectiveness of lab work (Helliari & Harrison, 2011; Wekwe et al., 2024). Moreover, insufficient training in laboratory techniques and safety measures results in ineffective teaching approaches and increases safety risks during experiments (Prabha, 2016; Vizyalona et al., 2024).

On the other hand, there is often a mismatch between curriculum expectations for lab work and the actual capabilities of schools. Insufficient time allocated for lab sessions within the curriculum limits hands-on learning opportunities, leading teachers to prioritize theoretical content over lab work (Chala, 2019; Mukaniyonsenga et al., 2023). Moreover, safety concerns about chemical handling can discourage teachers from conducting lab work (Ejidike & Oyelana, 2015). Additionally, large class sizes make it challenging to conduct lab activities (Mokotedi, 2013; Tomasik et al., 2013), while a lack of support from school administrators can hamper the effective implementation of lab activities (Endalamaw et al., 2017).

The challenges faced by teachers in implementing laboratory work in chemistry education can also be understood through the framework provided by Nivalainen et al. (2010) who have grouped these challenges under four categories: the limitations of laboratory facilities, insufficient content knowledge, understanding of instructional approaches and the general organization of lab work. In contrast, Yoon and Kim (2010) proposed another categorization, identifying five groups of challenges: lack of specific knowledge and skills, disappointment with external support, tensions between student interest and safety issues, reluctant attitudes of learners, and lack of interaction

Received: 03 February 2025

Revised: 12 February 2025

Accepted: 18 February 2025

478

among teacher and students. While the specific categories differ slightly, both studies underscore the complex interplay of factors that influence the successful implementation of lab work. However, as pointed out by Yalcin-Celik (2017), possessing strong content knowledge alone is insufficient for teachers to ensure effective laboratory teaching, they must also take into account their students, the curriculum, and the lab environment.

Significance of the study

Despite the extensive literature on laboratory work in education, there are very few studies that examine teachers' perceptions of experiments, and most of these studies focus on teachers' perceptions of laboratory work. A key aspect that sets this study apart is its focused examination of how chemistry teachers, in particular, perceive experiments. Furthermore, the Lebanese context is an example of an environment in which chemistry teachers' perceptions of experiments, their practices in conducting laboratory work as well as the challenges they encounter remain underexplored or even unexplored. Understanding all these aspects in the context of Lebanese chemistry education is crucial for developing targeted interventions that align with teachers' perceptions and practices, and for identifying effective strategies and areas where teachers may need additional support or resources. Such insights could be valuable for educational policymakers, school administrators, and curriculum developers in creating strategies that foster the effective implementation of lab work into chemistry teaching, thereby improving chemistry education in Lebanon.

Research questions

By answering the following research questions, this study sought to explore, from the perspectives of Lebanese chemistry teachers, their perceptions of experiments, the approaches they use to implement lab work as well as the challenges that hinder the effective integration of such activities:

- How do Lebanese chemistry teachers perceive experiments?
- How do Lebanese chemistry teachers implement lab work?
- What are the challenges that Lebanese chemistry teachers face in implementing lab work?

Methodology

The current study used a descriptive analytical approach and targeted Lebanese chemistry teachers in various Lebanese regions to identify their perceptions of experiments, their practices in implementing lab work, and the challenges they face. To achieve the research objectives, a questionnaire that was piloted before being implemented in Google Forms was used as a tool for data collection and analysis. It was distributed to teachers via WhatsApp in both French and English, given that the Lebanese education system is structurally bilingual and chemistry is taught in Lebanon in both languages.

The questionnaire was designed after reviewing previous studies such as those conducted by Welzel et al. (1998), Kane (2011), and Taoufik et al. (2016). It was divided into three sections. The first contained general information about the participants such as age, gender, academic level, teaching experience, grade(s) they teach, school size, class size, and training on effective lab work integration. The second section, titled "your perception of chemistry experiments", was designed to identify chemistry teachers' perceptions of experiments through a question aimed to reveal the teachers' definitions of an experiment. Based on Likert scale questions, the third section, titled

Received: 03 February 2025

Revised: 12 February 2025

Accepted: 18 February 2025

479

“implementation of laboratory work”, consists of 4 items and was used to identify teachers’ practices in conducting lab work as well as the challenges they encounter.

The research instrument was face- and content-validated by three experts in the field of chemistry education to ensure validity. Statistical analyses were performed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. A total of 118 chemistry teachers completed the questionnaires. The study yielded a Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.82, indicating a high level of internal consistency among the items in the measurement instrument.

Results and Discussion

A. Demographic and professional background of chemistry teachers

The demographic and professional backgrounds of the Lebanese chemistry teachers participating in the study, shown in Table 1, indicated that the average age of the participants is 29.72 years (standard deviation: 4.54), suggesting a relatively young-to-middle-aged teaching workforce. The moderate standard deviation indicated a homogeneous age distribution.

The average teaching experience is 5.86 years, with a standard deviation of 4.43, revealing a mix of seasoned and relatively newer educators, potentially reflecting a range of pedagogical styles and openness to conducting lab work. The gender distribution showed a significant majority of female teachers (74.58%) compared to male teachers (25.42%).

A substantial proportion of Lebanese chemistry teachers held advanced degrees, with 54.24% having obtained a master’s degree. Teaching Diploma holders made up 35.59% of the respondents, while those with Bachelor’s degrees accounted for 7.63%. A minimal percentage (2.54%) had a PhD. The high percentage of teachers with master’s degrees suggests a well-qualified teaching workforce, which could enhance the lab work implementation in educational practices.

The majority of participants work in medium-sized (44.07%) or large (43.22%) schools, while small schools account for only 12.71%. This distribution indicated that most participants are employed in larger schools. The school size can have a significant impact on the availability and frequency of chemistry laboratory usage. Larger schools typically have bigger budgets, better infrastructure, and more students, which can lead to greater investment in functional, well-equipped laboratories. In contrast, smaller schools may encounter financial or logistical challenges that limit the availability or regular use of chemistry labs. This limitation could affect how chemistry is taught, with smaller schools potentially relying more on traditional teaching rather than practical experiments.

The average class size is 22.81 students, suggesting a moderate sample size. In laboratory settings, having a medium class size is generally beneficial as it facilitates effective student management and reasonable access to resources. While smaller classes provide more individualized attention and better access to materials, which can enhance student learning, larger classes can lead to resource overload, making laboratory work more challenging to manage.

The majority of participants teach in secondary classes, with 78% teaching grade 10, 74.6% in grade 11, and 55.9% in grade 12. This distribution showed that the respondents are mainly involved in secondary education, where the implementation of lab work is more frequent than in middle school.

A significant proportion of the teachers (82.2%) did not attend any training courses on effective laboratory integration over the past five years, while 17.8% had participated in such training. Additionally, 76.27% of the respondents expressed a need for training on effective laboratory implementation. This indicated a substantial gap in professional development related to lab work, underscoring the need for more widespread and accessible training programs to equip teachers with the skills and knowledge necessary to effectively integrate lab work into their teaching practices.

Table 1. Participant demographics and general information

Age	M (mean)	29.72	
	SD (Standard Deviation)	4.54	
Years of teaching experience	M	5.86	
	SD	4.43	
Class size	M	22.81	
	SD	6.54	
		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	30	25.42%
	Female	88	74.58%
Highest degree obtained	BS	9	7.63%
	TD	42	35.59%
	MS	64	54.24%
	PhD	3	2.54%
School size	Small	15	12.71%
	Medium	52	44.07%
	Large	51	43.22%
Grades they teach	Grade 7	28	23.70%
	Grade 8	26	22.00%
	Grade 9	21	17.80%
	Grade 10	92	78.00%
	Grade 11	88	74.60%
	Grade 12	66	55.90%
Attended any training on effective laboratory implementation	Yes	97	82.20%
	No	21	17.80%
Training needs on effective laboratory implementation	Yes	90	76.27%
	No	28	23.73%

B. Results related to Research Question 1: How do Lebanese chemistry teachers perceive experiments?

A question aimed at identifying teachers' perceptions of chemistry experiments asked respondents to define the term "experiment" by selecting one definition from five options (Table 2).

Table 1. Which of the following suggestions best characterizes the meaning of "experiment"?

	Frequency	Percentage
A test designed to validate a hypothesis	35	29.66%
Implementing strategies to solve a problem	29	24.58%
An activity during which students manipulate material	26	22.03%
A precise observation of the reality	17	14.41%
An exploration through trial and error	11	9.32%
Total	118	100.00%

As shown in Table 2, the most selected definition was a test designed to validate a hypothesis (29,66%), suggesting that teachers view experiments primarily as a means to confirm or refute a hypothesis. This aligns with the traditional scientific method where hypotheses are formulated and tested through experiments (Abrahams & Millar, 2008; Mayo, 1996). Additionally, 24,58% of respondents perceive an experiment as an implementation of strategies to solve a problem. This indicated that teachers recognize the role of experiments in developing problem-solving skills.

On the other hand, 22,03% of teachers defined an experiment as an activity in which students manipulate material, compared to 14,41% who defined it as a precise observation of reality. These perceptions suggested that teachers emphasize the importance of hands-on experience and careful observations when conducting experiments. The definition highlighting exploration through trial and error is the least chosen (9,32%), suggesting that teachers may not fully embrace the idea of exploratory experiments. This could indicate a preference for more structured and guided laboratory activities.

Overall, the teachers' responses about their definitions of experiments provided key insights into their perceptions and understanding of experiments' role in chemistry education. These findings underscored a view of experiments as confirmatory rather than exploratory activities, suggesting that experiments primarily serve to verify existing knowledge. The focus on hypothesis testing might lead to more structured, less exploratory experiments which could impact students' development of investigation skills. Experiments are also seen as structured methods for problem-solving, with an emphasis on hands-on learning, highlighting the practical utility of experiments.

C. Results related to Research Question 2: How do Lebanese chemistry teachers implement lab work?

Several questions were designed to identify teachers' practices in conducting laboratory work. The first question addressed the frequency of lab work implementation in their chemistry teaching. Teachers were then asked whether they prefer solving exercises instead of conducting lab work or performing demonstrations rather than allowing students to carry out experiments. Lastly, teachers were asked to specify what they or the students do during laboratory activities.

Figure 1. How often do you implement lab work in your class?

The study showed that the majority of teachers (51.69%) conduct lab work occasionally, while 22.03% do so frequently, as illustrated in Figure 1. This indicated that lab work may be integrated as a supplementary activity rather than a central component of their teaching. Additionally, 23.73% of teachers noted that they rarely conduct lab work, and 2.54% reported that they never implement it. These findings may highlight various challenges that might hinder the frequent implementation of lab work.

As part of the ongoing investigation into teachers’ practices in conducting lab work, additional questions revealed the following preferences:

Table 3. Teachers’ preferences regarding their practices

You prefer to:	Yes	No
Solve classroom exercises instead of conducting lab work	81.36%	18.64%
Perform classroom demonstrations instead of having your students perform experiments on their own	75.42%	24.58%

A substantial majority of respondents (81.36%) prefer solving exercises in class rather than conducting practical work. Similarly, most teachers (75.42%) opt for classroom demonstrations instead of having their students perform experiments on their own. These findings suggested a preference among teachers for more controlled and teacher-centered instructional approaches over hands-on, student-centered activities. These preferences might stem from challenges that lead teachers to adopt teacher-centered strategies instead of lab work, which could limit opportunities for students to engage in active, inquiry-based learning. While solving exercises and observing demonstrations can support conceptual understanding, they may not fully develop students’ science process skills.

Regarding the implementation of lab work, the following table shows the responses from teachers.

Table 4. Implementation of laboratory work

When implementing lab work, specify if:					
It's you who					
	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
Design the procedure	35.59%	34.75%	21.19%	7.63%	0.85%
Select the necessary material	31.36%	31.36%	28.81%	7.63%	0.85%
Conduct the experiment	23.73%	25.42%	38.98%	11.02%	0.85%
It's the student who					
Designs the procedure	5.93%	16.10%	33.05%	18.64%	26.27%
Selects the necessary material	9.32%	23.73%	38.98%	16.10%	11.86%
Conducts the experiment	7.63%	31.36%	42.37%	10.17%	8.47%
Follows a procedure prescribed by the teacher	20.34%	43.22%	26.27%	5.08%	5.08%
The concepts to be learned are					
Taught before experiment	25.42%	37.29%	25.42%	9.32%	2.54%
Identified by the students alone	6.78%	17.80%	38.98%	26.27%	10.17%
Developed by you with the help of students	20.34%	33.90%	37.29%	8.47%	0.00%

As shown in Table 4, a significant majority of teachers, 70.34%, are actively involved in designing procedures (comprising 35.59% who always design procedures and 34.75% who often do so). Furthermore, 62.72% of teachers reported selecting the materials needed for experiments, with 31.36% always choosing the materials and another 31.36% often doing so. However, their involvement in conducting the experiments is more moderate, with 25.42% conducting them often and 38.98% doing so sometimes. These results suggested that teachers control lab activities significantly, especially in designing procedures and selecting materials, leading to limited opportunities for student autonomy and inquiry-based learning.

In contrast, students are less frequently engaged in designing procedures as reported by teachers. Only a small percentage of teachers (5.93%) indicated that students always design the procedure, while 16.10% noted that students often do so, and 33.05% stated that students are sometimes engaged in this task. According to teachers' responses, students are more involved in selecting the necessary materials, with 23.73% of teachers indicating that students often take part in this process and 38.98% stating they do so occasionally. Additionally, 31.36% of teachers mentioned that students often conduct experiments, while 42.37% indicated that they do so occasionally. When it comes to carrying out experiments, the majority of teachers (63.56%) noted that students either always or often follow a procedure prescribed by the teacher. Specifically, 20.34% reported that students always follow teacher-prescribed procedures, while 43.22% indicated they often do so.

Moreover, regarding learning concepts in relation to lab work, the data show that a significant majority of respondents (62.71%) reported teaching the targeted concepts before conducting experiments related to those concepts, with 25.42% always doing so and 37.29% often doing so. Students identifying concepts independently through lab work is less common, with 36.44% of

teachers (26.27% + 10.17%) rarely or never encouraging this. Interestingly, a notable portion of teachers, 54.24% (20.34% + 33.90%), reported always or often developing concepts with the help of students when implementing lab work.

Overall, the findings highlighted that teachers occasionally implement lab work, viewing it as a supplementary activity rather than an essential component of their teaching practices. Instead, they favor solving exercises and performing demonstrations over engaging students in hands-on experiments. This preference for structured, teacher-centered approaches over hands-on, student-centered activities, may limit students' opportunities to develop practical and critical thinking skills, which are crucial for a deeper understanding of chemistry.

Furthermore, the study revealed that teachers play a significant role in designing procedures and selecting materials, while student participation in these processes is notably limited. In contrast, students are more actively involved in conducting experiments. However, these experiments are of the "recipe" type where students follow a step-by-step procedure provided by the teacher. These findings underscored a predominantly teacher-centered approach to laboratory work, demonstrating that teachers implement lab work using the traditional expository style (Domin, 1999), a highly structured approach, where students follow predetermined instructions to achieve specific outcomes. These "cookbook" experiments are used to verify or confirm theoretical knowledge since teachers focus on teaching the targeted concepts before conducting experiments related to those concepts as the data show. These results align with previous research that has highlighted that verification, cookbook or recipe style is the most common way to implement lab work in schools (Köller et al., 2015; Tobin, 199; Wei & Li, 2017) where students simply follow instructions and procedural guidelines (Arnous & Ayoubi, 2018) for verifying or confirming existing theories (Prabha, 2016; Yeşiloğlu & Köseoğlu, 2020). Moreover, the limited level of student participation and conceptual engagement in practical work promoting lower-order cognitive skills, revealed in this study, is consistent with that of Abrahams and Millar (2008), who showed that teachers' emphasis on lab work rarely addressed the cognitive challenge of developing students' understanding of scientific inquiry procedures.

D. Results related to Research Question 3: What are the challenges that Lebanese chemistry teachers face in implementing lab work?

To identify the challenges teachers face in implementing laboratory work, teachers were asked to rank 11 specific challenges in order of importance. In this ranking system, a score of 1 indicates the most significant challenge, while a score of 11 indicates the least significant.

Table 5 summarizes these 11 challenges ranked by importance based on two criteria: the mean score, which reflects the average importance assigned to each challenge (with a lower score indicating greater significance), and the rank itself, where a rank of 1 corresponds to the most important challenge and a rank of 11 corresponds to the least important.

Table 5. Challenges of implementing lab work

Challenges	Mean	Rank
Lack of time	5.05	1
Class size	5.84	2
Limitations of laboratory facilities in your school including lack of equipment and chemicals	6.03	3
Absence of laboratory technician	6.07	4
Lack of students' practical skills	6.71	5
Low level of student autonomy	6.87	6
Classroom management	7.79	7
Safety concerns	7.91	8
Lack of adequate training in laboratory practices	8.03	9
Effort allocated for the preparation	8.78	10
Lack of specific knowledge and skills in designing and conducting lab work	9.31	11

As can be seen in Table 5, the major challenges identified as significant include the lack of time, which is perceived as the most pressing challenge due to the limited time available for conducting lab work. This encompasses the time needed for preparation, execution, and follow-up of experiments. Class size emerged as the second most significant challenge, as large class sizes complicate the management of practical activities, reducing their effectiveness and the quality of student follow-up. This can lead to difficulties in ensuring that all students are engaged and following safety protocols. Another significant barrier highlighted by teachers is the limitations of laboratory facilities, including the lack of equipment and chemicals, as they restrict the types of experiments that can be conducted and affect the quality of lab work. Furthermore, teachers were concerned about the absence of a laboratory technician to assist with the preparation and administration of lab work. This is particularly significant in Lebanon, where many schools lack a laboratory technician, which can add to teachers' workload and impact the overall safety and effectiveness of lab work. These findings underscored logistical and resource-related challenges that teachers frequently face in integrating lab work into their teaching.

Moreover, student-related factors appeared in the middle range of challenges. The lack of students' practical skills and their low level of autonomy highlight issues regarding student preparedness and participation. This suggests that many teachers perceive a gap in students' skills, which requires additional time and effort from teachers to provide guidance and supervision. Other challenges, such as classroom management during lab work and concerns about safety issues, rank relatively lower on the list of challenges. Additionally, the low ranking of challenges related to teacher competency underscored the dominance of logistical issues and resource constraints over pedagogical challenges.

In sum, this analysis revealed significant challenges that chemistry teachers encounter in implementing lab work. These findings align with previous studies highlighting the logistical and resource-related challenges that teachers face in integrating lab work into their teaching (Chala,

2019; Mokotedi, 2013; Nivalainen et al., 2010; Nkurunziza et al., 2023; Nsanzimana et al., 2021; Shana & Abulibdeh, 2020; Tomasik et al., 2013). Interestingly, the predominance of time constraints as the primary challenge is consistent with the findings of Ayoubi & BouJaoude (2006) who showed that, in Lebanon, the lack of enough time to teach chemistry, due to the limited time allocated to teach the extensive curriculum, forces the teachers to complete the curriculum, often at the expense of engaging students in meaningful hands-on activities.

Conclusion

This study investigated Lebanese chemistry teachers' perceptions of experiments, their practices in implementing lab work, and the challenges they face in doing so. The results revealed that teachers predominantly view experiments through a traditional scientific method lens, emphasizing hypothesis validation and problem-solving over exploration and discovery. These perceptions seem to influence the way they implement lab work in their classrooms. The study also highlighted that teachers occasionally conduct lab work, viewing it as a supplementary activity rather than an essential component of their teaching practices. Instead, they prefer solving exercises and performing demonstrations over engaging students in hands-on experiments. Their teaching practices in conducting lab work emerged as a predominantly teacher-centered approach where lab work is implemented as a confirmatory activity through a "recipe" style to verify previously taught concepts. On the other hand, the findings underscored logistical and resource-related challenges that teachers frequently face in integrating lab work into their teaching.

The conclusions drawn from this study have implications for educators, educational policymakers, curriculum developers, and teacher-training program designers in the field of chemistry education. Professional development and training programs are needed to promote student-centered approaches to lab work and emphasize the benefits of inquiry-based learning. Addressing the challenges identified in this study suggests systemic changes at the institutional and policy levels to ensure effective implementation of lab work. This, in turn, will contribute to improving the quality of chemistry education and student learning outcomes.

Limitations and Future Research Directions

This study focused on examining teachers' perceptions, practices, and the challenges they face in a traditional face-to-face laboratory setting, using a questionnaire to which only 118 responded. The use of quantitative data without relying on other qualitative data such as interviews or classroom observations could be a limitation of this research. Furthermore, the findings were limited to the context of a traditional face-to-face laboratory. It would therefore be interesting to conduct future research to investigate teachers' practices in implementing virtual and remote labs and to examine the impact of such implementation on student outcomes while combining both qualitative and quantitative data.

References

- Abd-El-Khalick, F., Boujaoude, S., Duschl, R., Lederman, N. G., Mamlok-Naaman, R., Hofstein, A., Niaz, M., Treagust, D., & Tuan, H. L. (2004). Inquiry in science education: International perspectives. *Science Education*, 88(3), 397-419.
- Abrahams, I., & Millar, R. (2008). Does Practical Work Really Work? A Study of the Effectiveness of Practical Work as a Teaching and Learning Method in School Science. *International Journal of Science Education*, 30, 1945-1969.
- Ajayi, P. (2008). Evaluation of the implementation of senior secondary school physics practical activities in Nigeria. *Research in Curriculum Studies*, 5, 90-99.
- Alema, B. G., Tesfamariam, G. M., Berhe, G. G., & Gebretsadik, T. T. (2024). Practices and challenges in implementing chemistry laboratory work in secondary schools: A review. *African Journal of Chemical Education*, 14(2), 31-60.
- Arnous, H., & Ayoubi, Z. (2018). Inquiry level of the undergraduate chemistry laboratory manuals in Lebanon. *West East Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(1), 13-22.
- Ayoubi, Z., & BouJaoude, S. (2006). A profile of pre-college chemistry teaching in Beirut. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 2(3), 124-143.
- BouJaoude, S. (2002). Balance of scientific literacy themes in science curricula: The case of Lebanon. *International journal of science education*, 24(2), 139-156.
- Chala, A. A. (2019). Practice and challenges facing practical work implementation in Natural Science subjects at secondary schools. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 10(31), 1-17.
- Crawford, G. L., & Kloepper, K. D. (2019). Exit interviews: Laboratory assessment incorporating written and oral communication. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 96(5), 880-887.
- Domin, D. S. (1999). A review of laboratory instruction styles. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 76(4), 543-547.
- Domin, D. S. (2007). Students' perceptions of when conceptual development occurs during laboratory instruction. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 8(2), 140-152.
- Duban, N., Aydogdu, B., & Yüksel, A. (2019). Classroom Teachers' Opinions on Science Laboratory Practices. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 7(3), 772-780.
- Ejidike, I. P., & Oyelana, A. A. (2015). Factors influencing effective teaching of chemistry: A case study of some selected high schools in Buffalo City Metropolitan Municipality, Eastern Cape Province, South Africa. *International Journal of Educational Sciences*, 8(3), 605-617.
- Endalamaw, D., Abebe, A., Meareg, G., (2017). An Investigation in to the Combined and Relative Influences of Some Selected Factors on Students' Performance in Physics. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(19), 52-59.
- Gericke, N., Högström, P., & Wallin, J. (2022). A systematic review of research on laboratory work in secondary school. *Studies in Science Education*, 59(2), 245-285. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057267.2022.2090125>

- Gott, R., & Duggan, S. (2007). A framework for practical work in science and scientific literacy through argumentation. *Research in science & technological education*, 25(3), 271-291.
- Harman, G., Cokelez, A., Dal, B., & Alper, U. (2016). Pre-Service Science Teachers' Views on Laboratory Applications in Science Education: The Effect of a Two-Semester Course. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 4(1), 12-25.
- Hassan, A. A., Ali, H. I., Salum, A. A., Kassim, A. M., Elmoge, Y. N., & Amour, A. A. (2017). Factors affecting students' performance in Chemistry: Case study in Zanzibar secondary schools. *International Journal of Educational and Pedagogical Sciences*, 9(11), 4086-4093.
- Helliar, A., & Harrison, T. (2011). The Role of School Technicians In Promoting Science Through Practical Work. *Acta Didactica Napocensia*, 4(2-3), 15-20
- Hofstein, A., & Hugerat, M. (2021). The role of the laboratory in chemistry teaching and learning. *Teaching and Learning in the School Chemistry Laboratory*, 1-15. Royal Society of Chemistry.
- Hofstein, A., Kipnis, M., & Abrahams, I. Z. (2013). How to learn in and from the chemistry laboratory. In A. Hofstein & I. Eilks (Eds.), *Teaching chemistry – A studybook* (pp. 153–182). Rotterdam: Sense.
- Hofstein, A., & Lunetta, V. N. (2004). The laboratory in science education: Foundations for the twenty-first century. *Science Education*, 88(1), 28–54.
- Hofstein, A., & Mamlok-Naaman, R. (2007). The laboratory in science education: the state of the art. *Chemistry education research and practice*, 8(2), 105-107.
- Hofstein, A., Shore, R., & Kipnis, M. (2004). Providing high school chemistry students with opportunities to develop learning skills in an inquiry-type laboratory: A case study. *International Journal of Science Education*, 26(1), 47-62.
- Johnstone, A. H., & Al-Shuaili, A. (2001). Learning in the laboratory; some thoughts from the literature. *University Chemistry Education*, 5(2), 42-51.
- Kane, S. (2011). Les pratiques expérimentales au lycée. Regards croisés des enseignants et de leurs élèves. *Radisma* (7), 1-26.
- Köller, H.G, Olufsen, M., Stojanovska, M., & Petruševski, V. (2015). Practical Work in Chemistry, its goals and effects. In Maciejowska, I., & Byers, B. (Eds.), *A guidebook of good practice for the pre-service training of chemistry teachers* (pp. 85-106). Faculty of Chemistry, Jagiellonian University.
- Lazarowitz, R., & Tamir, P. (1994). Research on using laboratory instruction in science. In D. L. Gabel (Eds.), *Handbook of research on science teaching and learning* (pp. 94-130). New- York: Macmillan.
- Lunetta, V. N., Hofstein, A., & Clough, M. P. (2007). Learning and teaching in the school science laboratory: An analysis of research, theory, and practice. In S. K. Abell & N. G. Lederman (Eds.), *Handbook of research on science education* (pp. 392 – 441). Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.

Marzin-Janvier, P., & Kermen, I. (2015). L'expérimental réel ou virtuel en classe de sciences. *Recherches en didactique des sciences et des technologies*, (12), 9-23.

Mayo, D. G. (1996). *Error and the growth of experimental knowledge*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.

McDonnell, C., O'Connor, C., & Seery, M. K. (2007). Developing practical chemistry skills by means of student-driven problem based learning mini-projects. *Chemistry education research and practice*, 8(2), 130-139.

Mokotedi, R.T. (2013). Beginning Primary School Teachers' Perspectives on the Role of Subject Specialization in Botswana Colleges of Education. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education* 6(1), 88-99.

Moutsakis, G., Paschalidou, K., & Salta, K. (2024). Chemistry laboratory experiments focusing on students' engagement in scientific practices and central ideas of chemical practices. *Chemistry Teacher International*. <https://doi.org/10.1515/cti-2024-0070>

Mukaniyonsenga, E., Uwizeyimana, D., Iyamuremye, A., Nsabayezu, E., & Niyonzima, F. N. (2023). Teachers' and Students' Experiences of Chemistry Practical in selected Day Secondary Schools in Nyarugenge District, Rwanda. *African Journal of Educational Studies in Mathematics and Sciences*, 19(1), 100-121.

Nakhleh M. B., Polles J., & Malina E., (2002). Learning chemistry in a laboratory environment. In Gilbert J. K., De Jong O., Justi R., Treagust D. F. and Van Driel J. H. (Eds.), *Chemical education: Towards research-based practice* (pp. 69-94). Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands.

Nivalainen, V., Asikainen, M. A., Sormunen, K., & Hirvonen, P. E. (2010). Preservice and inservice teachers' challenges in the planning of practical work in physics. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 21(4), 393-409.

Nkurunziza, J. B., Karegeya, C., Gakuba, E., Ntihakose, R., & Kampire, E. (2023). Challenges faced by chemistry teachers in conducting laboratory-based activities and their perceptions on preparing cost-effective chemicals used at lower secondary schools in Rwanda. *Rwandan Journal of Education*, 7(1), 103-118.

Nsanzimana, P., Ngendabanga, C., & Nkurunziza, J. B. (2021). Investigation of constraints faced by teaching and learning of chemistry in Nyarugenge district secondary schools: Quest for quality improvement. *GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 16(2), 110-121.

Pareek, R. B. (2019). An Assessment of Availability and Utilization of Laboratory Facilities for Teaching Science at Secondary Level. *Science Education International*, 30(1), 75-81

Prabha, S. (2016). Laboratory Experiences for Prospective Science Teachers: A Meta-Analytic Review of Issues and Concerns. *European Scientific Journal*, 12(34), 235-250.

Saad, R., & BouJaoude, S. (2012). The Relationship between Teachers' Knowledge and Beliefs about Science and Inquiry and Their Classroom Practices. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science & Technology Education*, 8(2), 113-128.

- Shah, I. (2007). *Making University Laboratory Work in Chemistry More Effective*. PhD thesis, University of Glasgow, Scotland.
- Shana, Z., & Abulibdeh, E. S. (2020). Science practical work and its impact on high students' academic achievement. *Journal of Technology and Science Education*, 10(2), 199-215.
- Sneddon, P. H., & Hill, R. A. (2011). Perceptions, views and opinions of university students about chemistry learning during practical work at school. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 12(3), 312-321.
- Taoufik, M., Abouzaid, A., & Moufti, A. (2016). Les activités expérimentales dans l'enseignement des Sciences Physiques : Cas des Collèges Marocains. *European Scientific Journal*, 12(22), 190-212.
- Tobin, K. (1990). Research on science laboratory activities: In pursuit of better questions and answers to improve learning. *School science and Mathematics*, 90(5), 403-418.
- Tomasik, J. H., Cottone, K. E., Heethuis, M. T., & Mueller, A. (2013). Development and preliminary impacts of the implementation of an authentic research-based experiment in general chemistry. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 90(9), 1155-1161.
- Vizyalona, A., Chirwa, G. W., & Nyoni, P. (2024). Challenges facing the implementation of Chemistry and Physics as separate and stand-alone subjects in the revised Secondary School curriculum in Malawi: A Case Study of Blantyre District. *International Journal of Educational Innovation and Research*, 3(2), 213-226.
- Wei, B., & Li, X. (2017). Exploring science teachers' perceptions of experimentation: implications for restructuring school practical work. *International Journal of Science Education*, 39(13), 1775-1794.
- Wei, J., Treagust, D. F., Mocerino, M., Lucey, A. D., Zadnik, M. G., & Lindsay, E. D. (2019). Understanding interactions in face-to-face and remote undergraduate science laboratories: a literature review. *Disciplinary and Interdisciplinary Science Education Research*, 1, 1-16.
- Wekwe, W., Mina, R., Masaulwa, J., Mafie, A., Mnahuva, K., Saidi, I., & Makanja, E. (2024). Investigation for Availability of laboratory technicians and laboratory Facilities for Public Secondary Schools in Dar es Salaam Region, Tanzania. *International Journal of Science, Technology and Society*, 12(1), 44-62.
- Welzel, M., Haller, K., Bandiera, M., Hammelev, D., Koumaras, P., Niedderer, H., Paulsen, A., Bécu-Robinault, K., & Von Aufschnaiter, S. (1998). Teachers' objectives for labwork. Research tool and cross country results working paper 6 from the *European project Labwork in Science Education, Targeted Socio-Economic Research Programme*, Project PL 95-2005. Available at: <https://www.idn.uni-bremen.de/pubs/Niedderer/1998-LSE-WP6.pdf>
- Yalcin-Celik, A., Kadayifci, H., Uner, S., & Turan-Oluk, N. (2017). Challenges faced by pre-service chemistry teachers teaching in a laboratory and their solution proposals. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 40(2), 210-230.

Yeşiloğlu, S. N., & Köseoğlu, F. (2020). Epistemological problems underlying pre-service chemistry teachers' aims to use practical work in school science. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 21(1), 154-167.

Yoon, H. G., & Kim, M. (2010). Collaborative reflection through dilemma cases of science practical work during practicum. *International Journal of Science Education*, 32(3), 283-301.